

Study of the Effects of Levetiracetam in Experimental Model of Alzheimer's Disease

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of this study is to study the cognitive effects and memory skills of Levetiracetam in comparison with Donepezil in experimental model of Alzheimer's Disease (AD).

Materials and Methods: The animals were divided into their respective groups of 6 mice each. Alzheimer's Disease was induced by Aluminium Chloride (AlCl₃) in male Wistar Rats in all groups. The assessment was done by three methods Morris Water Maze (MWM), Passive Avoidance and Y-Maze. Results were compared with the standard Donepezil. Statistical analysis was done by ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test and p < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: In all the three behavioural assessment methods the results of Levetiracetam group were comparable to the results of Donepezil group (Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90). There was a significant improvement in Levetiracetam group when compared to AlCl₃ group. Overall, Levetiracetam significantly improved the cognitive decline in the rats, showing its efficacy comparable to the standard drug Donepezil.

Conclusion: In this study it was concluded that Levetiracetam showed improvements in learning and memory, as demonstrated in the Morris Water Maze, Passive Avoidance, and Y-Maze tasks, showing that it has possibilities of becoming a promising agent for Alzheimer's Disease.

Keywords: Levetiracetam, Alzheimer's Disease, Y-Maze, Morris Water Maze, Passive avoidance.

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Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD), first described by Alois Alzheimer in 1906 [1], remains one of the most prevalent causes of dementia globally. AD is pathologically marked by the presence of amyloid β -peptides (A β) and tau protein aggregates, particularly affecting the hippocampus, a region central to memory and cognition [2].

This neurodegenerative disease often initiates in the medial temporal lobe and hippocampus, progressively impacting the temporal cortex, parietal regions, and neocortex. The ensuing neural destruction leads to impairments in memory, learning, and various other cognitive functions. [3,4]

Characteristic hallmarks of AD include extracellular amyloid plaques and intracellular neurofibrillary tangles, both of which play pivotal roles in disease onset and progression [5]. Additionally, neuronal loss within the nucleus basalis of Meynert reduces

choline acetyltransferase (ChAT) activity, further diminishing acetylcholine levels at synapses, a factor strongly associated with cognitive decline in AD. [6]

AD is a significant health concern, affecting approximately 70% of dementia cases worldwide and with rising prevalence among the elderly population, particularly in countries with ageing demographics such as India. [7,8]

Despite extensive research efforts, current pharmacological treatments—primarily acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (e.g., Donepezil, Rivastigmine, Galantamine) and NMDA receptor antagonists (e.g., Memantine)—provide only symptomatic relief without addressing underlying disease mechanisms [9].

This study explores the cognitive and memory-enhancing potential of Levetiracetam compared to

Donepezil within an experimental Alzheimer's model, assessing its effectiveness in mitigating the cognitive deficits typically observed in AD.

Materials and Methods

A total of 18 Male Wistar rats; Scientific Name-Rattus Norvegicus of weight 150-200 grams.

Animals were obtained from authorized dealer in Lucknow.

The animals were maintained in cages, under a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and 45-55% relative humidity, with a 12-hour light/dark cycle. They were fed with standard pellet diet and water ad libitum.

Ethical Consideration: All experiments were performed after approval from Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of Era's Lucknow Medical College as per the guidelines of Animal Care by CPCSEA.

Drugs and Chemicals

Levetiracetam: Tablet Levetiracetam was purchased from local market by the brand name Levipil 500mg manufactured by Sun Pharma Laboratories Ltd. It was dissolved in distilled water and was administered to experimental animals at a dose of 90mg/kg/day orally with the help of oral gavage tube for 12 weeks [10].

Donepezil: Tablet Donepezil was purchased local market by the brand name Donecept 10mg manufactured by Cipla Ltd. It was dissolved in distilled water and was administered to experimental animals at a dose of 0.9mg/kg/day orally for 12 weeks [11].

Aluminium Chloride: Solution of Aluminium Chloride was made fresh every day for administration purpose. AlCl_3 was administered to rats at a dose of 175 mg/kg, orally from day 0 for 60 days. It was dissolved in distilled water and was administered orally according to the bodyweight. The dose of AlCl_3 was taken from previous literature reports [12]. This dose is shown to induce AD at faster rate with low incidence of mortality.

Methodology

After purchasing the animals, they were put on a quarantine period for 14 days. Then the rats were trained for 1 week prior to the start of the experiment on Morris water Maze, Y-Maze and Passive Avoidance Apparatus. After the training phase, rats were divided into 3 groups of 6 rats each. Total number of 18 rats were taken.

- Alzheimer's Disease was induced in all the groups.
- All the drugs were dissolved in distilled water and were administered to the animals orally.

Group 1: Control –given Distilled Water + AlCl_3 orally for 8 weeks

Group 2: Standard: Donepezil orally at a dose of 0.9mg/kg for 12 weeks + AlCl_3 orally for 8 weeks

Group 3: Levetiracetam orally at a dose of 90mg/kg for 12 weeks + AlCl_3 orally for 8 weeks

Aluminium Chloride for induction of Alzheimer's Disease as well as the drug treatment (Levetiracetam and Donepezil) was started from the Day 0 of the experiment and were administered with the help of oral gavage tube.

Aluminium Chloride was continued till 60 days while the drugs treatment was continued till 90 days.

The standard and the test drug were administered 45 minutes before Aluminium Chloride solution administration in their respective groups.

Assessment of Memory deficits and Learning skills was done on Day 0, Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 by using Morris water Maze, Y-Maze and Passive Avoidance Apparatus.

Behavioural Analysis

Passive Avoidance Response Apparatus: [13]

The Passive Avoidance task which aggravates fear that is used to assess learning and memory in animal models. It involves learning to inhibit a response to avoid an aversive stimulus [14].

The apparatus is consisted of a box having dimensions 27 cm x 27 cm x 27 cm with three walls of wood and one wall (front) of Plexiglas. It features a grid floor which is made up of 3 mm stainless-steel rods set 8 mm apart. In the center of the grid floor there is a wooden platform which is shock free area with dimensions 10 cm x 7 cm x 1.7 cm [15]. The box was illuminated with a 15 W bulb during the experimental period. Electric shock of 50Hz, 1.5mA was delivered to the grid floor.

Procedure: For training period, the rat was placed on the wooden block and electric shock (50 Hz, 1.5 mA, 2 s) was administered through the grid floor on stepping down. Retention test was done after 24 hours. For Acquisition trial, a wooden platform is placed on the grid floor which was carrying foot shock (50 Hz, 1.5 mA). Each rat is placed on the wooden platform, and time taken by the rat to step down and place all four paws on the grid floor carrying shock was recorded as Step Down Latency (SDL) which is a measure of retention. Step down Latency (SDL) in seconds was recorded as end point.

Increase in SDL is considered as a parameter of learning. A cut-off time of 60 seconds was chosen. Rats showing SDL in the range of >15 seconds during the training session were taken for

acquisition and the retention tasks. Assessment was done on Day 0, Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90.

Morris water maze (MWM): It is a validated test used for measuring spatial learning and memory. Since many years this technique has been used to motivate learning by escaping from water [16].

The Morris Water Maze (MWM) is used to determine spatial learning for small animals that depends on distal cues to navigate from starting points around the perimeter of an open swimming space to find a submerged escape platform. Spatial learning is estimated by repeated trials and reference memory is estimated by preference for the platform area. [17]

It consist of a circular swimming pool with 117 cm in diameter, 60 cm high. It was filled with water upto 25 cm. Two hundred milliliters of milk or any coloring agent which is nontoxic was added to make the water opaque so that the animal is not able to see the platform. An 8×8 cm Plexiglas escape platform, was submerged 0.5 cm under the water level. During the training session, each animal was placed in the pool for 60 seconds and was allowed to swim and find the escape platform; this enabled the animal to get habituated to the training environment. The escape latency (EL) from placing the animal into the pool to escape onto the platform was assessed for each trial. If the rat is not able to find the platform within 120 seconds, it was placed manually onto the platform for 30 seconds. During the test session, the rat was placed into the pool and the time taken by the rat to find the platform was measured, which was considered as a parameter to assess memory retention [18]. Cut off time of 60 seconds was taken. Assessment was done on Day 0, Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90.

Y-Maze: It is has been known that spontaneous alternation is a parameter to assess spatial working memory [19].

Y-maze consists of three arms having dimensions 90 cm long× 90 cm wide × 76 cm high. One arm was randomly illuminated by a 15 W lamp suspended in the end of each arm and two arms was dark in which electric shock was supplied. It has been designed to make the animal to learn to discriminate among the arms and learn to reach the correct arm, the illuminated one. During the behavioral training period, each animal was placed at the intersection of the three arms and trained to choose to enter in randomly bright arm in the first 10 s, and the choice

of the darken arm was count as a 'discrimination error'. Whenever the animal made an error, it received a brief electric foot shock (35 V, 4.5 mA), until it entered the bright arm. It was done by switching the unit on or by rotary program selector till the animal reaches the goal in illuminated arm. Test session was done and Correct Arm Entries (CAE) were counted for each animal. Nine out ten CAE served as learning criterion. [20].

Statistical Analysis: The data obtained was tabulated and subjected to descriptive analysis. The different groups were compared using ANOVA (Analysis Of Variance) followed by Post Hoc Dunnett T3 Test. All statistical analysis were done using Graph pad Prism software (version 6.02). P value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results:

Effect of Test Drugs on Escape Latency by Morris Water Maze Response: When ANOVA was applied followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test, there was no significant difference in escape latency in all the groups at day 0 (Baseline value) (p=0.1519).

A significant increase in escape latency was observed in the Control (AlCl₃) group at Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 when compared to Day 0 which showed a significant deterioration in learning and memory (p<0.0001).

In the Donepezil (Standard) Group there was no significant difference in the escape latency at Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 when compared to the baseline values which demonstrated a significant attenuation in the cognitive impairment (p=0.3376). Control group showed that there was significant increase in escape latency at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 when compared to the Donepezil group. In Levetiracetam group, there was significant increase in escape latency at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 when compared to the baseline (Day 0) value (p=0.0044). [Table 1 and Figure 1]

There was no significant difference in the escape latency at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 in the Levetiracetam group when compared to Donepezil Group and there was a significant decrease in escape latency in Levetiracetam group when compared to Control group (p<0.0001). This demonstrates that Levetiracetam significantly improved the cognitive deficits. [Table 1 and Figure 1]

Table 1: Effect of Levetiracetam on Escape Latency by Morris Water Maze Response:

Groups	Day 0 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	Day 30 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	Day 60 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	Day 90 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	p Value F Value
Control AlCl ₃	2.500±0.7071	12.67±1.633*	21.83±4.021*	29.17±0.9832*	p<0.0001 F=157.5
Donepezil (Standard)	1.833±0.4082	2.417±0.5845+	2.333±0.7528+	2.250±0.5244+	p=0.3376 F=1.193
Levetiracetam	1.917±0.6646	3.583±0.9704*+	3.417±0.5845*+	3.083±0.7360*+	p=0.0044 F=5.980
ANOVA	p=0.1519 F=2.143	p<0.0001 F=143.5	p<0.0001 F=126.6	p<0.0001 F=2364	

* When compared to Day 0/ Baseline Values (p<0.05), # When compared to standard; (p<0.05), + When compared to Control; (p<0.05)

Figure 1: Effect of Levetiracetam on mean escape latency in seconds by Morris water maze

Effect of Test Drugs on Step down Latency by Passive Avoidance Response Apparatus: When ANOVA was applied followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test, there was no significant difference in Step down latency in all the groups at day 0 (Baseline value) (p=0.8330). A significant reduction in step down latency was observed in the Control (AlCl₃) group at Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 when compared to Day 0 (p<0.0001) which demonstrated that Aluminium Chloride caused impairment in learning and memory.

In the Donepezil (Standard) Group there was no significant difference in the step down latency at Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 when compared to the baseline values (p=0.5802). Control group showed that there was significant decrease in step down latency at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 when compared to the Donepezil group which

demonstrated an improvement in cognitive function. In Levetiracetam group there was no significant difference in step down latency at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 when compared to the baseline value (p=0.4747). Levetiracetam group showed significant improvement in learning and memory as compared to control group (p<0.0001). [Table 2 and Figure 2] It was observed that there was no significant difference in the step down latency at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 in the Levetiracetam group when compared to Donepezil Group and there was significant increase in step down latency in Levetiracetam group when compared to Control group (p<0.0001). This demonstrated that Levetiracetam significantly improved the cognitive decline when assessment was done on Passive Avoidance Response Apparatus. [Table 2 and Figure 2]

Table 2: Effect of Levetiracetam on Step down Latency by Passive Avoidance Response:

Groups	Day 0 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	Day 30 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	Day 60 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	Day 90 Mean±SD (Time in secs)	p Value F Value
Control AlCl ₃	54.50±4.461	7.500±1.517*	2.417±0.4916*	1.833±0.4082*	p<0.0001 F=685.9
Donepezil (Standard)	55.67±1.862	53.17±2.858+	54.33±3.445+	55.00±4.147+	p=0.5802 F=0.6702
Levetiracetam	54.83±3.430	51.83±2.927+	52.00±5.657+	52.17±1.941+	p=0.4747 F=0.8665
ANOVA	p=0.8330 F=0.1850	p<0.0001 F=638.8	p<0.0001 F=350.9	p<0.0001 F=762.0	

* When compared with Day 0/ Baseline Value (p<0.05), # When compared with standard; (p<0.05), + When compared with Control; (p<0.05)

Figure 2: Effect of Levetiracetam on mean Step Down latency in seconds by Passive Avoidance Apparatus

Effect of Test Drugs on Number of Correct Arm Entries by Y-Maze Response Apparatus: When ANOVA was applied followed by Dunnett’s multiple comparisons test, there was no significant difference in number of Correct arm entries in all the groups at day 0 (Baseline value) (p=0.6738).

A significant reduction in number of Correct arm entries was observed in the Control (AlCl₃) group at Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 when compared to Day 0 (p<0.0001) which demonstrated that Aluminium Chloride caused impairment in discrimination learning. In the Donepezil (Standard) Group there was no significant difference in number of Correct arm entries at Day 30, Day 60 and Day 90 when compared to the baseline values which demonstrated an improvement in learning and memory

(p=0.2146). Control group showed that there was significant reduction in number of Correct Arm Entries at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 when compared to the Donepezil group. In Levetiracetam group there was no significant difference number of Correct arm entries at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 when compared to the baseline value (p=0.1700). [Table 3 and Figure 3] It was observed that there was no significant difference in the number of Correct arm entries at Day 30, Day 60, and Day 90 in the Levetiracetam group when compared to Donepezil Group and there was significant increase in number of correct arm entries in Levetiracetam group when compared to Control group (p<0.0001). This demonstrated that Levetiracetam significantly improved the cognitive dysfunction [Table 3 and Figure 3].

Table 3: Effect of Levetiracetam on Number of Correct Arm Entries by Y-Maze Response:

Groups	Day 0 Mean±SD (CAE)	Day 30 Mean±SD (CAE)	Day 60 Mean±SD (CAE)	Day 90 Mean±SD (CAE)	p Value F Value
Control AIC ₃	9.667±0.5164	5.000±0.8944*	3.167±0.9832*	1.833±0.4082*	p<0.0001 F=127.8
Donepezil (Standard)	9.500±0.5477	8.500±1.049+	9.000±0.8944+	9.333±0.8165+	p=0.2146 F=1.628
Levetiracetam	9.333±0.8165	8.167±0.4082+	8.667±1.211+	8.667±0.8165+	p=0.1700 F=1.854
ANOVA	p=0.6738 F=0.4054	p<0.0001 F=32.50	p<0.0001 F=59.74	p<0.0001 F=206.8	

* When compared with Day 0/ Baseline Value (p<0.05), # When compared with standard; (p<0.05), + When compared with Control; (p<0.05)

Figure 3: Effect of Levetiracetam on mean number of Correct Arm Entries (CAE) by Y-Maze Apparatus

Discussion

This study aimed to explore the cognitive effects of Levetiracetam compared to Donepezil in an experimental Alzheimer's Disease (AD) model. The results demonstrated that Levetiracetam significantly improved cognitive performance, showing comparable results to Donepezil, a standard treatment for AD. This discussion will evaluate the findings in relation to existing research, establish key correlations, and highlight the limitations and gaps in the study.

Several studies support the potential cognitive benefits of Levetiracetam in neurodegenerative disorders such as AD. Zheng et al. (2022) reported that Levetiracetam alleviated cognitive decline in AD models by improving neuronal network function [21]. This finding aligns with the current study's results, which showed improved escape latency in the Morris water maze (MWM) and better performance in the Y-maze. Similarly, Belcastro et al. (2007) [22] confirmed that Levetiracetam

modulates synaptic function and reduces hyperexcitability, a common feature in AD, consistent with our study's findings. Although this study found Levetiracetam's cognitive benefits to be on par with Donepezil, previous research highlights differences in their mechanisms of action. Donepezil works by enhancing cholinergic activity, whereas Levetiracetam acts on synaptic vesicle proteins, particularly SV2A, to regulate neurotransmitter release. This mechanistic divergence might result in different long-term impacts on neurodegeneration, warranting further investigation.

Additionally, Sanchez et al. (2012) [23] and Shi et al. (2016) [24] support the notion that Levetiracetam can reduce amyloid-β plaque formation and protect against synaptic loss, further correlating with the cognitive benefits observed in the present study. In particular, these studies emphasize that Levetiracetam's effects extend beyond symptom relief by targeting underlying disease processes like

synaptic plasticity and hyperexcitability, as seen in AD.

One of the major limitations of this study is the lack of biochemical markers to better understand the molecular mechanisms underlying Levetiracetam's action. For instance, measurements of amyloid- β , tau protein levels, or synaptic markers like SV2A were not included. Without this molecular data, it is difficult to fully elucidate how Levetiracetam achieves its cognitive benefits. Previous studies, such as those by Korolev (2014) [3] and Bozoki et al. (2012) [4], underscore the importance of linking behavioral improvements to molecular outcomes, suggesting that future studies should integrate such biomarkers. Furthermore, while the sample size of 18 rats (6 per group) provided statistically significant results, it remains relatively small compared to other preclinical studies, potentially limiting the generalizability of these findings. Expanding the sample size in future research would help strengthen the validity of the results and mitigate risks like Type II errors.

Another limitation is the short duration of the study. AD is a chronic and progressive disease, and it is essential to evaluate whether the cognitive benefits of Levetiracetam persist over time or diminish with prolonged use. Long-term studies, such as those by Folch et al. (2016) [6] and Bishara et al. (2015) [5], are needed to determine if Levetiracetam can offer sustained protection against cognitive decline, or if tolerance develops after extended treatment periods.

Conclusion

In summary, this study contributes to the growing evidence supporting the use of Levetiracetam in treating cognitive symptoms of AD. Improvements in learning and memory, as demonstrated in the Morris Water Maze, Passive Avoidance, and Y-Maze tasks, underscore its potential as a therapeutic agent. However, several limitations—such as the absence of molecular data, a small sample size, and short follow-up periods—limit the depth of the current findings. Future research should focus on overcoming these gaps by incorporating biochemical markers, increasing the sample size, and conducting long-term studies to comprehensively evaluate the neuroprotective mechanisms and efficacy of Levetiracetam in AD treatment.

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